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24th-25th September 2021 University of Belgrade

2nd International UNIFood Conference

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The word of welcome

Dear colleagues,

We would like to welcome you to the **2nd UNIFood International Conference –UNIFood2021**. We hope that this gathering will engage not only academics, but also the stakeholders from all the relevant industries and business sectors, serving as a meeting point and a platform for proliferation of new ideas and development of new partnerships.

The first UNIFood conference, organized as national, was established 2018. year as one of the events in honor of the **210th Anniversary** celebration of the **University of Belgrade** that ranked at Shanghai list on 35th place for the 2017 year in subject *Food Science and Technology*. The University of Belgrade has been recognized as a leading international scientific institution by LERU when it was selected to be a member of CE7, an informal network of seven Central and Eastern European universities collaborating with LERU on key research and education challenges. Furthermore, University of Belgrade joined European University Alliance Circle U. Following the European Commission's launch of the European Universities initiative, a group of research-intensive universities has entered into a Memorandum of Understanding with the intention of establishing a new university alliance: Aarhus University, Humboldt University of Berlin, King's College London, UC Louvain, University of Belgrade, University of Oslo and Université de Paris.

We are pleased that you have decided to take part in this mutual conversation, where many will present their recent work, through poster sessions, oral communications or simply by asking questions. One of the goals of this Conference is cooperation between academia and food industry. Food scientists, technologists, researchers, nutritionists, engineers and entrepreneurs will exchange their knowledge about the latest advances in all aspects of food production, processing, sustainability, safety and security, nutrition and health, hi-tech equipment, ethics and knowledge transfer supporting environment. At this meeting, over 200 participants from 23 countries will take part.

Belgrade, one of the oldest city in the Europe, always young, at the confluence of the Sava and Danube rivers, will be your host. At the confluence of new ideas and experiences we again wish you a warm welcome.

Sincerely,

Prof. Dr Mirjana Pešić

*President of the Scientific Committee
of UNIFood2021*

Prof. Dr Ivanka Popović

Rector of the University of Belgrade

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PRESERVATIVES IN LIQUID HERBAL DIETARY SUPPLEMENTS AND EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT

Sladjana, Š, Vojvodić^{1,2}, Dejan, Ž, Kusonić¹, Branislava, U, Srdjenović Čonić^{1,3}, Ljilja, D, Torović^{1,4}

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Dietary supplements could contain preservatives, chemicals widely used to prolong shelf life of sensitive products, and thus present potential health risk. An investigation of actual usage levels of preservatives in dietary supplements was conducted to provide concentration data for exposure assessment, further combined with product usage instructions declared by the manufacturers.

Eighty eight herbal dietary supplements purchased in pharmacies in Novi Sad in 2018 (36) and 2021 (52) were liquids with either sorbates or benzoates on ingredients list. The method of analysis was HPLC-UV. Daily intake of sorbic and benzoic acid was expressed as percentage of their respective acceptable daily intakes (ADI) of 11 and 5 mg/kg body weight/day.

Conformity evaluation revealed three supplements containing benzoic acid in excess of the maximum permitted level of 2000mg/L (4244-6811mg/L). Benzoic acid ADI was exceeded by three supplements, one intended for adults (148%), one for adolescents (132%) and children (206%), one if used by preschool children (156%) and toddlers (300%). No supplements exceeded sorbic acid ADI by any of the population groups. Mean exposure of adults, adolescents, children and preschool children ranged from 23 to 31% of ADI for benzoic acid, and from 5 to 10% of ADI for sorbic acid, whereas exposure of toddlers was substantially higher (77 and 14%, respectively). High exposure level (95th percentile) reached 84% (benzoic) and 23% (sorbic acid) in population of preschool children. Mean exposure from 31 samples intended for toddlers, excluding nine samples demanding pediatrician's recommendation for dosing, corresponded to 77% of ADI for benzoic and 14% for sorbic acid. Only three supplements were intended for infants, one of which reached 70% of benzoic acid ADI.

However, more realistic approach considering usually short period of supplements' usage showed significantly lower exposure and no health concern.

Keywords: Herbal dietary supplements, Preservatives, Exposure assessment, HPLC